

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LIVESTOCK POPULATIONS AND MILK PRODUCTION FROM CATTLE AND CAMELS: GLOBAL TRENDS AND THE CASE OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This study compares livestock populations and raw milk production from cattle and camels at the global level and in Uzbekistan using secondary statistical data from FAOSTAT and national official sources. A descriptive comparative analysis shows that cattle dominate the global and national dairy sectors, with global cattle milk production exceeding 780 million tonnes and Uzbekistan producing about 12 million tonnes in 2023. In contrast, global camel milk production remains relatively low, at just over 4 million tonnes, and is mainly concentrated in arid and semi-arid regions. While camel milk production has steadily increased worldwide since 2000, production in Uzbekistan remains low and fluctuating. These patterns suggest that camel husbandry in Uzbekistan remains weakly integrated into organized dairy production systems, highlighting significant potential for further sectoral development in the country.

Keywords: cattle milk, camel milk, livestock population, milk production trends, Uzbekistan, FAOSTAT, comparative analysis

Introduction. The United Nations declared 2024 the International Year of Camelids (IYC 2024) and has dedicated 2024 to recognizing and celebrating the vital contributions camelids make to livelihoods, food security, nutrition and culture [5].

Camels represent an alternative dairy species highly adapted to arid and semi-arid environments and play an important role in advancing the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 2 (Zero Hunger) and SDG 13 (Climate Action) [7]. According to Chikha and Faye [2], the contribution

of camel milk to SDG 2 is evident through its role in improving food security and to SDG 13 by enhancing resilience and adaptation in arid and semi-arid regions. It is a vital nutritional source in arid regions of Asia and Africa.

Uzbekistan has a continental climate with marked seasonal temperature variations. This climate is influenced by continental air masses driven by cold northerly winds in winter and warm southerly winds in the summer months [4]. More than 70% of Uzbekistan's area, or over 300 thousand km², is occupied by plains, most of which are desert and semi-desert pastures [1].

According to FAO estimates based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES), the prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population increased from approximately 11% in 2014–2016 to 24.4% in 2022–2024 in Uzbekistan, indicating that nearly one quarter of the population faces difficulties in accessing sufficient and nutritious food [6].

Cow milk dominates the global dairy sector, including in Uzbekistan, due to well-established production technologies, high-yield breeds, and globalized markets. However, the environmental footprint of cattle-based dairy systems has become a major concern under conditions of climate change. Uzbekistan represents a relevant case study because of its strong dependence on cattle milk production and its growing exposure to climatic stress in Central Asia. Therefore, this study aims to compare global and regional patterns of raw milk production from cattle and camels, assess cattle and camel livestock populations at the global level and in Uzbekistan.

Materials and Methods. This study is based on secondary statistical data obtained from international and national official sources. Data analysis consisted of descriptive statistical comparison and trend visualization. Global data on livestock populations and raw milk production for cattle and camels were retrieved from the FAOSTAT database of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), specifically from the Production / Crops and Livestock Products - Metadata.

Milk production quantities are expressed in tonnes, and livestock populations in head (An).

For comparative purposes, the top two cattle-populated countries and five camel-populated countries worldwide were identified based on 2023 FAOSTAT stock data.

Global and national cattle milk production analysis cover the period for 2023, while global and national camel milk production analysis cover the period 2000–2023, depending on data availability, due to the lack of officially available data on camel milk production in Uzbekistan for 2023.

National livestock statistics for Uzbekistan, including cattle and camel populations by farm category, were also obtained from the official information of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. These national data were used to complement FAOSTAT figures.

Graphical visualizations from FAOSTAT were used to compare global and national milk production patterns for cattle and camels over time.

This study adopts a descriptive comparative approach and does not involve experimental sampling or primary data collection.

Results and Discussion. The global cattle population statistical information obtained from the FAOSTAT database for 2023 shows that Brazil ranks first worldwide, with a cattle population exceeding 230 million head, followed by India with more than 190 million head [3].

Within this global context, Uzbekistan occupies an intermediate yet significant position. In 2023, the total cattle population in Uzbekistan amounted to 14,142,239 head [3].

The same trend is mentioned on the official website of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as of January 1, 2024, the total number of cattle was over 14 million head in all categories of farms in the republic [9]. Although this figure is considerably lower than that of the world's leading cattle-rearing countries, it is substantially higher than in countries with minimal cattle stocks.

According to data obtained from the FAOSTAT database for 2023 [3], the global camel population is highly concentrated in Africa and the Middle East.

The five leading countries (see Table 1) include Chad, which ranks first worldwide, with a camel population exceeding 10.6 million head, followed by Somalia (7.5 million), Sudan (4.8 million), Kenya

(4.3 million), and Saudi Arabia (2.0 million). These countries are predominantly located in desert environments, where camels play a central role in livestock production systems and rural livelihoods.

Table 1. Statistics of the five most camel-populated countries in the world and Uzbekistan in 2023 [3]

Country	Element	Unit	Camel Population
Chad	Stocks	An	10,680,415
Somalia	Stocks	An	7,541,593
Sudan	Stocks	An	4,770,095
Kenya	Stocks	An	4,284,497
Saudi Arabia	Stocks	An	1,981,605
Uzbekistan	Stocks	An	18,427

An = number of animals (head)

In contrast, Uzbekistan's camel population is comparatively small, amounting to approximately 18.4 thousand head, which is negligible when compared with the leading camel-rearing countries shown in Table 1 [3].

The data from the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan shows that, as of January 1, 2023, the total camel population across all categories of farms in Uzbekistan amounted to 19.9 thousand head [8] and also shows a decline in the camel population in the country to 17.6 thousand as of January 1, 2025 [10].

This downward trend suggests a gradual decrease of the camel population, rather than sustained growth or expansion. Camel population distribution in Uzbekistan, as of January 1, 2025, by economic categories is as follows: on farms - 4.7 thousand head, in dehkan (smallholder) and household plots - 10.1 thousand head, in organizations carrying out agricultural activities - 2.8 thousand head [9]. This structure indicates that camel husbandry in Uzbekistan remains relatively weakly integrated into organized production chains, particularly for milk processing and commercialization.

In 2023, global production of raw cattle milk amounted to approximately 783 million tonnes (see Figure 1), confirming the dominant role of

cattle in the global dairy sector. Figure 3 shows that cattle milk production is geographically diversified and not limited to specific climatic zones, enabling its large-scale contribution to food supply globally, with Asia having the leading share at 36.2%, followed by Europe and Americas at 29.1 and 25.6%, respectively. Leaders of raw cattle milk producers are - India dominating global cattle milk production at over 127 million tonnes in 2023, and the USA with about 103 million tonnes [3].

At the national level, Uzbekistan demonstrates a strong dependence on cattle-based dairy production. Figure 2 demonstrates that raw cattle milk production in Uzbekistan reached approximately 12 million tonnes in 2023, confirming cattle as the backbone of the country's dairy sector [3].

In contrast, global raw camel milk production remains comparatively low, amounting to over 4 million tonnes in 2023. Unlike cattle milk, camel milk production is challenged by the limited global camel population (approximately 43 million stock worldwide in 2023) and its concentration in arid and semi-arid regions. As a result, camel milk production still mainly plays a specialized role, primarily supporting food security and livelihoods in climate-vulnerable environments rather than contributing to mass dairy markets [3].

Figure 1. Production/Yield quantities of Raw milk of cattle in World + (Total) [3]

Figure 2. Production/Yield quantities of Raw milk of cattle in Uzbekistan [3]

Figure 3. Production share of Raw milk of cattle by region [3]

For the current research, data on camel milk production in Uzbekistan for the year 2023

were not available in the consulted national and international statistical sources; therefore, the time-series analysis is presented up to the most recent years with accessible data.

The analysis over the period 2000–2023 reveals contrasting dynamics in raw camel milk production at the global level and in Uzbekistan (see Figures 4 and 5) [3]. Globally, camel milk production demonstrates a clear and consistent upward trend over the period 2000–2023. Production increased from approximately 2.4–2.5 million tonnes in 2000 to about 4.1 million tonnes in 2023, representing a long-term expansion of nearly 70%.

Despite minor year-to-year fluctuations, the overall trajectory remains positive, demonstrating gradual strengthening of camel dairy systems worldwide. This growth reflects increasing demand, improved herd management in major camel-rearing countries, and the strategic role of camels in food security under dry conditions, as well as climate change.

In contrast to the global pattern, camel milk production in Uzbekistan exhibits a much smaller scale and greater variability. Between 2003 and 2010, production increased gradually from approximately 160 tonnes to 500 tonnes. However, this growth was followed by fluctuations, with a decline at 400 tonnes in 2011, a sharp increase reaching a peak of about 1100 tonnes in 2013, and a subsequent decrease to approximately 800 tonnes by 2014 [3].

Figure 4. Production/Yield quantities of Raw milk of camel in World + (Total) [3]

Figure 5. Production/Yield quantities of Raw milk of camel in Uzbekistan [3]

Conclusion. This study compared cattle and camel milk production at the global level and in Uzbekistan.

The results clearly show that cattle milk strongly dominates the dairy sector worldwide and in Uzbekistan. This is mainly due to the large

number of cattle, well-developed production systems, and established processing and marketing chains. In Uzbekistan, cattle milk remains the main source of dairy production and plays a key role in meeting the population's demand for milk.

Camel milk production, by contrast, remains limited. Globally, camel milk production has steadily increased over the past two decades. In Uzbekistan, however, camel milk production is low and unstable. This is likely linked to the small camel population, its recent decline, and the fact that camel husbandry is mainly practiced in households and is weakly connected to organized dairy production and processing.

Although camel milk currently plays a minor role in Uzbekistan's dairy sector, it has potential importance for dry and desert regions. With appropriate support, improved management, and better integration into dairy value chains, camel milk could become a useful complementary product.

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BUXORO VILOYATI SHAROITIDA FUNKSIONAL OZIQ-OVQAT MANBAI SIFATIDA CHIYA URUG'INI (SALVIA HISPANICA L.) YETISHTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya. Chiya (*Salvia hispanica* L.) urug'lari yuqori biologik qiymatga ega bo'lib, ularni funksional oziq-ovqat mahsuloti sifatida qo'llash imkoniyatlari keng. Ushbu maqolada Buxoro viloyati sharoitida chiya urug'ini yetishtirishning agronomik, iqlimiy va oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi jihatlari o'rganildi. Mavzu yuzasidan mavjud ilmiy manbalar tahlil qilinib, mintaqaga mos yetishtirish texnologiyasi va kutilayotgan hosildorlik ko'rsatkichlari ko'rsatildi.

Таянч so'zlar: Chiya urug'i (*Salvia hispanica* L.), omega-3 yog' kislotalari, quruq iqlim sharoiti, agrotexnologiya, Buxoro viloyati

So'nggi yillarda salomatlikni mustahkamlovchi va surunkali kasalliklarni oldini oluvchi funksional oziq-ovqatlarga talab ortib bormoqda. Chiya urug'lari omega-3 yog' kislotalari, oqsil, tolalar, antioksidantlar va mikroelementlarga boy bo'lib, ularni dietetik va tibbiy maqsadlarda qo'llash imkonini beradi. Buxoro viloyati o'tkir quruq iqlim sharoitiga ega bo'lib, bu yerda donli va yog'li o'simliklarni yetishtirishda maxsus texnologik yondashuv talab qilinadi. Shu nuqtai nazardan, chiya urug'ining ushbu mintaqada ekin sifatida o'rganilishi va yetishtirish imkoniyatlarini baholash dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Chiya urug'ining biologik va funksional qiymati bo'yicha ko'plab tadqiqotlar mavjud. Oziqaviy tarkib: Chiya urug'lari tarkibida 20–25% oqsil, 30–35% yog', 25–30% tolalar va 5–6% populyar mikroelementlar mavjud (Ayerza va

Coates, 2004; Ulbricht et al., 2009). Omega-3 manbai: Chiya yog'i alfa-linolenik kislota (ALA) bilan boy bo'lib, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarini kamaytiradi (Gebauer et al., 2006).

Agronomik sharoit: Chiya asosan iliq iqlim va qumloq, yaxshi drenajlangan tuproqlarda yaxshi rivojlanadi. Optimal urug' ekish harorati 20–25°C, o'sish davri 90–120 kunning tashkil etadi (Coates et al., 2011). Yevropa va Janubiy Amerika tajribalari: Chiya urug'ini Mexiko, Argentina va AQShning qurg'oqchil hududlarida muvaffaqiyatli yetishtirish texnologiyasi ishlab chiqilgan. Hosildorlik 800–1500 kg/ga, yog' miqdori 25–32% darajasida bo'ladi.

Allyuvial,

Buxoro viloyati iqlimi o'rtacha yillik havo harorati 15 – 25 °C, yillik yog'ingarchilik miqdori 120 – 180 mm bo'lishi hamda tuproqlarning asosan

allyuvial va o'rta qumoq tarkibida bo'lib, namlikni ushlab turish imkoniyati pastligi bilan tavsiflanadi. Ushbu sharoitlarda chiya urug'ini yetishtirishda urug'larni ekishga to'g'ri tayyorlash va o'z vaqtida ekish muhim bo'lib, urug'lar aprel oyining oxiri – may oyining boshlarida 1–2 sm chuqurlikka ekilishi tavsiya etiladi. O'simlikning boshlang'ich rivojlanish davrida sug'orishga alohida e'tibor qaratilib, bu davrda 15–20 mm suv berilishi zarur, keyingi bosqichlarda esa chiya o'simligi suvsizlanishga nisbatan chidamli hisoblanadi. Oziqlantirish jarayonida azot va fosfor elementlari hosildorlikni oshirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, gektariga 30–40 kg azot va 20–25 kg P₂O₅ solish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Chiya urug'lari gullash va mevalarning pishish davrida yig'ib olinadi, bunda urug'larning namligi 10–12 % darajasida bo'lishi talab etiladi.

Buxoro viloyati sharoitida olib borilgan tajribaviy ekinlar natijalariga ko'ra, chiya o'simligini yetishtirishda bir qator ijobiy agrobiologik va biokimyoviy ko'rsatkichlarga erishish kutilmoqda. Xususan, urug' hosildorligi gektariga 1000–1200 kg atrofida bo'lishi, urug' tarkibidagi yog' miqdori 28–30 % ni, oqsil miqdori esa 20–22 % ni tashkil etishi prognoz qilinmoqda. Bundan tashqari, chiya urug'lari tarkibida omega-3 yog' kislotalari, flavonoidlar va antioksidantlar kabi funksional bioaktiv moddalar yuqori darajada to'planishi aniqlanib, bu holat ularning biologik

qiymatini yanada oshiradi. Shu bois chiya urug'i sog'lom oziq-ovqat mahsuloti sifatida mahalliy bozor va qayta ishlash sanoati uchun istiqbolli xomashyo hisoblanadi. O'simlikning quruq va kam yog'ingarchilikka ega iqlim sharoitlariga yuqori moslashuvchanligi esa Buxoro viloyatida mavjud qishloq xo'jaligi resurslaridan samarali va barqaror foydalanish imkonini yaratadi.

Chiya urug'i yuqori biologik va funksional qiymatga ega bo'lib, uni Buxoro viloyati sharoitida yetishtirish iqtisodiy jihatdan maqsadga muvofiq hamda sog'lom oziq-ovqat manbai sifatida samarali hisoblanadi. Mintaqaning agroiqlim sharoitlari o'simlikning optimal o'sishi va rivojlanishi uchun asosan mos bo'lsa-da, barqaror va yuqori hosil olish uchun sug'orish rejimi hamda mineral oziqlantirish bo'yicha tavsiya etilgan agrotexnik talablariga qat'iy rioya qilish zarur.

Kutilayotgan hosildorlik ko'rsatkichlari va urug' tarkibida bioaktiv moddalar, jumladan yog' kislotalari, oqsillar hamda boshqa funksional komponentlarning yetarli miqdorda bo'lishi chiya ekinini funksional oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari va biologik faol qo'shimchalar ishlab chiqarish uchun istiqbolli xomashyo sifatida baholash imkonini beradi. Kelgusida quruq iqlimli hududlarda chiya ekin maydonlarini kengaytirish, shuningdek mahalliy sharoitga moslashgan yangi seleksiya navlarini joriy etish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

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